

ABOUT THE MECHANISM OF MICA SPLITTING

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ABSTRACT

The article provides an overview of experimental and theoretical methods for splitting mica using muscovite as an example, starting from the 30s of the last century. From a review of these works, it follows that when chopping (splitting) crystals, the structure of its surface layer, which is different from the structure of the main crystal, is not taken into account. In 2018, we proposed an empirical model by which it is theoretically possible to calculate the thickness of the surface layer of solids and its anisotropy. Subsequently, it turned out that the thickness of the surface layer is equal to the length of the nanocrack, which is formed in any solid body, obtained by any method in nature or artificially, and along which the crystal splits. The muscovite splitting model we propose includes: determination of the melting temperature of muscovite mica; determination of adhesion energy using the obtained equations; splitting of muscovite in the cleavage plane due to the creation of frictional forces in the rollers that exceed the adhesion energy.

Keywords: mica, muscovite, surface layer, cleavage, adhesion energy, cleavage plane, melting point.

Introduction

Micas are a group of aluminosilicate minerals with a layered structure, of which we will consider muscovite - $KAl_2(AlSi_3O_{10})(OH)_2$ [1, 2], which is widely used in industry and in everyday life [3-5]. GOST 10698-80 Mica [6] is a standard that applies to the main types of mica (muscovite and phlogopite) and establishes types, grades, basic parameters and primary areas of application in the national economy. GOST 10918-82. Mica plates and parts [7] applies to mica plates of arbitrary shape and rectangular mica parts without internal holes (except for radio components, television mica and muscovite mica for “3000” devices), used as a dielectric material and various types of insulation (electrical, thermal, hydrothermal). GOST 26858-86. Electrical insulating mica paper [8] covers electrical insulating mica paper made from muscovite and phlogopite without a binder, used for the manufacture of electrical insulating materials. GOST 25045-81. Electrical insulating materials based on plucked mica [9] applies to electrical insulating materials made from plucked mica

from muscovite and phlogopite, intended for use in electrical machines and apparatus. For the materials listed above, it is necessary to split (exfoliate) mica, which we will review below.

The purpose of this article is to review experimental and theoretical methods for mica cleavage and to propose our new model for muscovite cleavage.

Method of splitting (stratification) of mica (muscovite)

Obreimov I.V. back in 1930, he proposed a method for determining the surface tension of muscovite [10]. The idea of this work is as follows. A plate splits off from the crystal along the cleavage plane, which, under the influence of the moment of forces acting against the forces of surface tension, is partially bent. This plate can be used as a dynamometer to measure the peeling force. Indeed, the work done by the moment M acting at the edge of a plate of thickness t (Figure 1), when the separation region is lengthened by an amount δx , is equal to $M = \partial\delta\varphi/\partial x = M \delta x \partial^2\varphi/\partial x^2$.

Figure 1. - Scheme of detachment of a layer from a crystal [10]

This work under equilibrium conditions must be equal to the change in the surface energy of the system, i.e. $2\gamma \delta x$. Taking into account the expression for the moment bending the plate $M = Et^3/12(1-x^2) \partial^2\varphi/\partial x^2$, we

can obtain an expression for γ :

$$\gamma = \frac{Et^2}{24(1-x^2)} \frac{\partial^2\varphi}{\partial x^2}, \quad (1)$$

which was used in [10]. In the last formula, E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, ϕ is the angle between the tangent to the curved contour of the split-off plate and the direction of movement of the mouth of the developing crack. In [10], the splitting of mica, which is known to have perfect cleavage, was studied; in this case, the value of $\partial^2\phi/\partial x^2$ was determined using the interferometric technique. According to Obreimov's measurements, the free energy of muscovite crystals in air is 1500 erg/cm², and in vacuum - 20000 erg/cm². Kuznetsov [11] found an error in Obreimov's calculations and, correcting it, obtained for the free energy in air and vacuum, respectively, 375 and 5000 erg/cm². Metsik M.S. [12] carried out a detailed analysis of the determination of the work of cleavage of muscovite, namely: the dependence of the work of cleavage on the thickness of the sample; dependence of the splitting work on speed; influence of humidity; influence of air pressure; influence of temperature. From the experimental materials given in [12], it is clear that the work of splitting mica crystals - muscovite:

- a) increases with increasing lift-off speed;
- b) at significant (average) speeds it increases with increasing thickness of the torn plate;
- c) decreases with increasing relative air humidity;
- d) does not depend on air pressure within the range of 725 - 2 mm Hg. Art., if the water vapor pressure remains unchanged.
- e) depends on the temperature at which the separation occurs.

The only satisfactory explanation of these facts can only be an explanation based on the idea of electrification of the crystal surfaces at the moment of their separation. A detailed work [13] is devoted to this point, where the question of the origin of charge during the splitting of crystals was discussed from the standpoint of the conservation law:

- the charge arises due to the flow of electrons from the crystal to the electrode (or vice versa);
- the electron charge is an induced charge that arises due to the appearance of an electric field in the crystal.

The article [13] states that in 1930 Obreimov [10] noticed that mica becomes electrified during splitting. Methodology of Obreimov I.V. Crystal cleavage was successfully applied to direct measurements of the surface energy of many crystalline bodies by Gilman [14]. The main measurements in [14] were performed by forced splitting of the crystal along a certain crystallographic direction, which was carried out due to the development of a previously created crack. The force (F) required for crack propagation according to the pattern shown in Figure 1 was measured using a sensitive dynamometer device. It is shown in [14] that under conditions when cleavage occurs in the low temperature region ($T = -195^\circ\text{C}$), the energy (dW) spent on lengthening the crack by the amount dL consists of two terms - the increase in the elastic energy of the splitting halves of the crystal (dW_U) and free energy of the resulting surfaces (dW_S): $dW = dW_U + dW_S$. The total energy of the breaking off halves of the crystal turns out to be equal to $W_U = F^2L^3/6EI$, where E is Young's modulus, and $I = \omega t^3/12$, ω is the width of the sample. Hence $dW_U = F^2L^2/2EI dL$. Quantity $dW = Fd\delta_0$, where $\delta_0 = \partial W_U/\partial F|_{x=0} = FL^3/3EL$. Thus, $dW = F^2L^2/EI dL$. Taking into account the written relations and the fact that $dW = \gamma\omega dL$, it is easy to obtain:

$$\gamma = \frac{6F^2L^2}{E\omega^2t^3}. \quad (2)$$

The results [14], obtained in experiments at -196°C , are given below:

Table 1.

Surface energy of some crystals [14]						
Substance	LiF (100)	MgO (100)	CaF ₂ (111)	CaCO ₃ (100)	Si (111)	Zn (0001)
γ , erg/cm ²	340	1200	450	230	1240	105

The works [15-19] summarize the physics of mica splitting in the twentieth century. In [16], a model of fine (ultrafine) splitting of muscovite mica in a highly elastic polymer was used, taking into account coarse splitting of mica crystals up to 1.0 μm in thickness and ultrafine (ultrathin) splitting up to 0.01 μm . The polymer mass is loaded into the gap between the rollers and at the same time small muscovite mica crystals 50 microns thick are loaded. The main condition for splitting at the first stage: the difference between the forces of cohesion and adhesion must be greater than or equal to the tensile strength of the peeled micas. Delamination of mica to a thickness of 1-3 microns occurs due to the creation of frictional forces in the rollers and the appearance of an elastic wave in the split part. The thickness of the split mica in this case will tend to the limiting value of $\sim 1.0 \mu\text{m}$. For finer splitting of mica crystals (ultra-thin delamination), it is rolled repeatedly in the polymer mass with a continuous decrease in the gap between the rollers. In this case, the high adhesive bond

between the crystal and the polymer mass on the roll separates them along the embryonic cracks. The process of splitting mica crystals with a highly elastic polymer, like any technological process, can be considered as an open nonlinear system under conditions of moving away from thermodynamic equilibrium with a large number of degrees of freedom. During the splitting process, the number of split-off crystals decreases with a decrease in the advancing wave and the size of the split-off mica with a constant gap between the rollers. When ultra-thin splitting of mica, multiple rolling is necessary while reducing the gap between the rollers. The work [20] proposed a method for splitting mica crystals by treating it with hydrogen peroxide followed by splitting with a water or air jet, characterized in that, in order to increase the yield of a product with the largest usable area, the mica is pre-soaked in water before treatment with hydrogen peroxide. In [21], a method for splitting mica by exposure to an electric field and mechanical processing is proposed, characterized in that before

grinding the mica is exposed to an electric field at a frequency of 50 Hz, a current density of 0.01-0.10 A/cm², a temperature of 40-100 °C. Recently (2019), work [22]

conducted a study by splitting mica in a manner similar to Obreimov’s approach [10], but using modern research methods (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic illustration showing (a) the setup of a mica-cleaved sample, (b) the side profile of the cleavage front, and (c) the orientation of the quartz wedge [22].

[22] tested mica sheets of various thicknesses to determine the intrinsic strength of mica, which is directly related to the surface energy of the basal cleavage planes of the mica crystal. The load-displacement curves for a set of mica are shown in Fig. 3. Each of these curves shows the initial increasing load pattern during approximately the first 10 mm of displacement, as well as the observed load drop at the eventual 10-15 mm displacement.

Observations of the samples after testing showed that cleavage spreads as follows:

$$\frac{F}{b} \approx G \left(1 + \frac{\mu}{\alpha} \right). \tag{3}$$

where α is a geometric coefficient related to the contact angle between the wedge surface and the mica sheet, which can be described as:

$$\alpha = 3 \left(\frac{u}{h} \right)^{3/2} \cdot \left(\frac{G}{6Eh} \right)^{3/4}. \tag{4}$$

where u is the thickness of the wedge, G is the shear modulus, E is Young’s modulus, and μ is the coefficient of friction between the wedge and mica.

Figure 3. Dependence of load on displacement during shearing of homogeneous mica layers. Temporary increases in force (*) due to edge defects or localized tears were excluded from the analysis [22].

In Figure 4 shows the regression of the normalized force on $h^{3/4}$, which represents a linear function and fits Equation (3) well.

The critical rate of deformation energy release in air, measured in [22], was $0.81 \pm 0.38 \text{ J/m}^2$. Obreimov, using surface energy analysis, determined this energy as 0.76 J/m^2 [10]. Similarly, in [18, 19], the measured

mica-mica adhesion energy was in the range of 0.6 to 0.8 J/m^2 at a humidity of 20% and above.

The results of the study [22] show that near the tip of a crack, a situation is possible when the magnitude of the driving force for crack propagation changes sharply, which will manifest itself in an increase in macroscopic fracture toughness.

Figure 4. Average force depending on the chip thickness $h^{3/4}$ [22].

Theoretical aspects of crystal splitting (destruction)

The main direction of research in fracture mechanics is the processes of crack propagation (see above). This direction has been developed in detail and includes linear and quasi-linear fracture mechanics (Griffiths theory [23] and the theory taking into account the Irwin correction [24] for plastic deformations), and nonlinear processes of crack propagation (crack opening criterion, invariant Cherepanov-Rice integral [25, 26]), which are presented in a large number of works: articles, monographs and dissertations [27-33]. These works provide a review (with a large number of references to well-known works) and analysis of existing theoretical methods for studying the strength of solids and the duration of crack growth. The kinetics of crack

development significantly depends on the interaction of the sequence of loads (amplitudes) of variable loading (see Fig. 3). Thus, overload modes help slow down the growth of a crack, while underload modes can increase it. The overload-underload and underload-overload modes also affect the kinetics of crack growth. Random external loading contains all these elements and therefore there is a need to study the kinetics of crack growth with the application of an external load in the form of spectra (see Fig. 3). Methods for studying layered structures can be divided into three large groups: analytical (mainly asymptotic) methods, numerical methods, and numerical-analytical methods.

The first direction is characterized by the fact that the hardness and softness of the layers are taken into account, as well as its relative thickness (see Fig. 4),

which allows the use of asymptotic expansion methods (asymptotic splitting method [34]). The advantages of this approach include the fact that the result usually results in analytical expressions that are convenient for research. The development of computer technology has led to the widespread use of standard computing packages based on the finite element method. From the large mass of similar works, it is worth highlighting studies [35, 36], characterized by a detailed analysis of the results obtained. In contrast to asymptotic methods, numerical-analytical solutions of contact problems for layered elastic bodies do not imply any restrictions imposed on the relative thickness or relative stiffness of the layers [37]. In this case, numerical calculations are used only at the final stage of the solution.

Our muscovite splitting model

From a review of previous works, it follows that when chopping (splitting) crystals, the structure of its surface layer, which is different from the structure of the main crystal, is not taken into account. What is the thickness of this layer? This issue was resolved in ultrahigh vacuum on the surfaces of atomically smooth crystals using the following methods: low-energy electron diffraction (LEED), where only the layers of atoms

closest to the surface (~ 0.5 nm) take part in the formation of the LEED pattern; X-ray diffraction at grazing angles, when the angle of incidence is equal to or less than the critical angle of total internal reflection (for example, for silicon this layer depth is 3.2 nm, and for gold – 1.2 nm) [38].

Only in 2018, we proposed an empirical model, according to which it is theoretically possible to calculate the thickness of the surface layer R(I) of solids [39] and its anisotropy [40, 41]. Subsequently, it turned out that the thickness of the surface layer is equal to the length of the nanocrack R(I) = L_{nm}, which is formed in any solid, obtained by any method in nature or artificially. The thickness of the surface layer R(I) and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} are given by us by the empirical formula [39-41]:

$$R(I) = L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu [M]. \quad (5)$$

In equation (5), you need to know one parameter - the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$ - a constant, so that the dimension (R(I) = [m]). Using formula (5), we calculate R(I) = L_{nm} (Table 2) for muscovite. The axle ratio is taken into account here - 0.574: 1: 2.221.

Table 2.

Parameters R(I) = Lnm of muscovite.

Muscovite	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	R(I) _a = L _{nma} , nm	R(I) _b = L _{nmb} , nm	R(I) _c = L _{nmc} , nm
KAl ₃ Si ₃ O ₁₂ H ₂	398,308	2,93	13,3 (26)	23,11 (26)	51,3 (26)

From Table 2 it follows that the layer R(I) < 100 nm is a nanostructure according to the Gleiter classification [42]. The thickness of the R(I) layer along the surface a (cleavage plane) is 13.3 nm = 0.0133 μm , which coincides with the ultrathin (ultrathin) cleavage of muscovite - up to 0.01 μm [16]. Number of layers in table. 2 is given in parentheses and is equal to $n = R(I)_{a,b,c}/a, b, c = 26$.

In the R(I) layer with crystal atoms, reconstruction or relaxation occurs, associated with the restructuring of the surface [38]. Moreover, a relaxed surface is characterized only by a change in interplanar distances, while a reconstructed surface may have a difference in the arrangement of near-surface atoms. Size effects in the R(I) layer are determined by the entire collective of atoms in the system (collective processes). Such

“quasi-classical” size effects are observed only in nanoparticles and nanostructures [43]. Now consider the muscovite splitting model. Figure 5 shows that the hexagonal symmetry of an individual muscovite network is lost upon transition to a double silicate layer formed by two hexagonal networks interconnected by aluminum atoms - Al (here O potassium ion - K).

It should be taken into account that the lines that mark the hexagons in Figure 5 do not represent connections, but only connect the vertices of the tetrahedra of the upper and lower layers. Hydroxyl ions are located in the center of each hexagon, however, due to the dense packing of atoms, which occurs when two tetrahedral networks are superimposed, these ions in adjacent layers of atoms are not located directly below one another.

Figure 5. Central part of the double silicate layer muscovite structure [44].

As a result, the true sixth-order axis inherent in one mesh cannot be common to a pair of meshes. Such a displacement of the grids reduces the symmetry to monoclinic. Obviously, when muscovite splits, the layers disintegrate exactly along the planes in which the K atoms are located (i.e., in the plane of the vector $a - \{001\}$). It was shown in [45] that the surface energy of a bulk crystal γ_2 , with an accuracy of 3%, is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (6)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of muscovite ($T_m = 1548 \text{ K}$).

In the R(I) layer, it is necessary to take into account the size effect and the surface energy of the R(I) layer becomes equal to γ_1 [46]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2(1 - R(I) / R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) shows that the surface energy of the R(I) layer is three times less than the surface energy of the main crystal. To separate the R(I) layer from the rest of the crystal, it is necessary to expend energy, which is called the Dupre adhesion energy [47]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1,3\gamma_2, \quad (8)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase interface, which is negligible due to a second-order phase transition.

Using formulas (6) – (8), we calculate the parameters for muscovite.

Table 3.

Energy parameters of muscovite.

Muscovite	$\gamma_a, \text{ J/m}^2$	$\gamma_b, \text{ J/m}^2$	$\gamma_c, \text{ J/m}^2$	$W_{aa}, \text{ J/m}^2$	$W_{ab}, \text{ J/m}^2$	$W_{ac}, \text{ J/m}^2$
$\text{KAl}_3\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}\text{H}_2$	0,622	1,083	2,404	0,809	1,408	3,125

In the cleavage plane, the adhesion energy is $W_{aa} = 0.809 \text{ J/m}^2$. If we turn to work [22] (see above) $W_{aa} = 0.81 \pm 0.38 \text{ J/m}^2$, in Obreimov [10] $W_{aa} = 0.76 \text{ J/m}^2$, in works [18, 19] $W_{aa} = 0, 6 \pm 0.8 \text{ J/m}^2$. In other words, all measurements turn out to be equal within the error, but the methods [10, 18, 19, 22] are very labor-intensive and require many samples and different experimental conditions (mica thickness, cutting speed, temperature, electric and magnetic fields, etc.). Equations (6) – (8) make it possible to determine the adhesion energy from the melting point of natural muscovite from any deposits with any impurities. Muscovite does not melt well. However, in [48], a unique experimental complex was developed and created for conducting thermophysical and technological studies of high-temperature non-metallic materials in the temperature range of 600 K - 6000 K and pressure $3 \cdot 10^2 \text{ MPa}$. The complex includes various heating sources (laser, resistance furnace and electric arc); low (vacuum) and high pressure chambers; automated high-speed 10^{-5} sec data collection and processing system; high-temperature technological

furnaces and two blackbody models (maximum operating temperature 3000 K and 3700 K, patents No. 1759126, 1996 and No. 1124682, 1995). To this we can add Patents [49-51].

Thus, the muscovite splitting model includes: determining the melting point of muscovite mica using methods [48-51]; determination of adhesion energy W_{aa} using equations (6) – (8); splitting of muscovite in the cleavage plane due to the creation of frictional forces in the rollers $W_f > W_{aa}$ according to the method [16].

Conclusion

Any solid body (and even liquid) has a surface, for which a significant role is played by the surface layer, which determines the interaction of the solid body with the external environment. The splitting of a solid begins from the surface layer, the structure of which may differ markedly from the main crystal. This issue is considered in the article for muscovite, for which there is a lot of experimental data. The model we proposed, which is

much simpler than the experimental studies carried out, can be used for any solids.

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